

SOCIAL SCIENCES

ENGINEERING AND TECHNICAL MEASURES TO REDUCE THE ACTIVATION OF LANDSLIDE PROCESSES

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Abstract

The problem of studying the conditions of formation, mechanism of development and prediction of formation and activation of landslide processes is one of the most urgent issues, and its solution is of great importance to preserve the lives of people living in mountainous areas. Landslide process that develops due to loss of stability of a slope (slope) is a movement of a mass of rocks, composing this slope, on the other part of both parts of the material connection. Landslide process can be defined as a sequence of phenomena or states of the landslide body, and landslide phenomenon as a fixed state of the landslide body. Competent installation of protective engineering structures helps to protect the territory from landslides for a long time. Experience shows that the most effective way is the complex of measures and the use of different protective materials against landslides. Thus, the effectiveness of gabions and geogrids is significantly increased with the use of geotextile sheets, which acts as an excellent reinforcing material and prevents mutual penetration of technological layers.

Keywords: key words: Landslide process, erosion, slopes, landslide control structures.

The problem of studying conditions of formation, mechanism of development and forecast of formation and activation of landslide processes is one of the most actual issues, and its solution is of great importance for preservation of life of people living in mountainous areas. Landslide processes are widespread, especially in the territory of Azerbaijan, the diverse nature of formation, and the scale and intensity of their manifestation reflects the naturally developing changes in the relief of mountainous folded areas.

According to the definition of the theory of any geological process by I.V. Popov [1], the theory of landslide processes can be defined as a system of basic laws and regularities that determine their physical essence, the possibility and conditions of occurrence, stages of activation and attenuation (process occurrence in time) depending on the interaction with the environment.

The object of the theoretical study is the landslide process landslide. The term landslide is often understood as both a process and a geological body [2].

Landslide process that develops due to the loss of stability of a slope (slope) is the movement of a mass of rocks, composing this slope, on the other part of both parts of the material bond. The landslipped mass is called a landslide body, and the surface along which the landslide occurs is called a slip surface or a displacement surface [3].

A landslide process can be defined as a sequence of events or states of a landslide body, and a landslide event as a fixed state of a landslide body. The "state" is understood as the structure and properties of the object at an arbitrary point in time. Then the phenomenon is the structure and properties of the object at this moment, and the process is a change in the structure and properties of the object. Currently, there are many definitions of landslide process [3].

As can be seen, different authors define the content of the concept of "landslide process" in different

ways. But, despite this, the following positions are common:

- 1) landslide process is a displacement of masses of rocks down the slope;
- 2) the main driving force is the weight of the shifting rocks;
- 3) the movement of landslide masses on the slope occurs in the form of sliding or in some cases flow;
- 4) displacement of the landslide occurs without loss of contact between the moving rocks and the fixed bedrock.

Landslides are secondary exogenous geological processes (EGP), i.e. processes whose development conditions are prepared by primary EGP [2]. Landslides can occur: as a result of weathering (contact of the lithosphere with the atmosphere); as a result of coastal scour (contact of the lithosphere with the surface hydrosphere); as a result of earthquakes (contact of the near-surface area of the lithosphere with its deep parts); due to human economic activity (contact of the lithosphere with the technosphere).

Numerous additional factors that cause the development of landslide processes, by the nature of action can be combined into the following groups [7]:

1. Factors that create the environment in which slope processes develop. These are: rock complexes; folded and discontinuous tectonic structures; lithogenetic, tectonic and other fracturing of rocks; degree and mode of watering; spatial correlation of tectonic disturbances with orientation and steepness of the slope, etc. The group of factors includes the following. In general, this group of factors is determined by engineering geological conditions of the territory.

2. Factors changing the state and properties of rock massifs. These are processes of unloading and decomposition of rocks caused by erosion and abrasion dissection of the territory; processes of weathering and mechanical suffusion in all variety of their action; processes of leaching and karst; modern tectonic movements causing increased rock fragmentation in

tectonic and adjacent zones; increased watering of rocks due to atmospheric and groundwater, especially along fractures, contacts, interlayers and lenses.

3. Factors that change the magnitude and distribution of stresses in the rocks of the slope. These include all the factors of the previous group, as the change of rock properties is reflected in their stress state; changes in height and steepness as a result of intensive and irregular modern tectonic uplifts; development of processes of deep or lateral erosion, abrasion, etc.; seismicity, causing temporary but significant redistribution of stresses in the rocks of the slope; hydrodynamic pressure.

4. Technogenic factors affect both the strength of slope rocks and their stress state as a result of creation of various excavations, dumps, vertical planning, loading from the weight of structures; vibration from ma-

chinery and explosions; additional moisture due to unorganised runoff of economic water, leaks, irrigation, etc.; open and underground mining of mineral deposits. Technogenic factors are more often characterised by a relatively local area of action, but they manifest themselves in a more active form. Each of them has a natural analogue, and its effect on the occurrence of slope processes is assessed through appropriate indicators and criteria.

Seismic phenomena contribute to the activation of landslide processes [8].

Landslides are the displacement of soil masses under the action of their own gravity down the slope. According to statistics, landslide movement occupies 17% of the total share of dangerous geological processes. A variety of methods are used to prevent this hazard [6].

Figure 1. - Dependence of maximum seismic landslide volume (logarithmic scale) on earthquake magnitude

Considering the causes of landslides in Azerbaijan, we can cite the classification of landslides according to the factors of landslide development.

1. Hydrogeological - influence of groundwater.
2. Climatic - influence of atmospheric precipitation.
3. Erosion - the influence of bank erosion by surface watercourses.
4. abrasion - the influence of surface watercourses.
4. Abrasion - influence of erosion of lakes and reservoirs.
5. Seismic - influence of earthquakes.
6. Artificial (technogenic) - influence of human activity.
7. Mixed - i.e. combination of the listed factors, the main factor is put in the first place, then the additional factor, for example: climatic-hydrogeological, artificial-climatic, erosion-climatic, etc.

Landslide control measures include design of structures and works for landslide protection of buildings, settlements, transport highways and main engineering communications, as well as unoccupied areas of prospective or ecological importance. Landslides are a natural and regular process of formation of the relief of the Earth's crust, arising on slopes as a result of interaction of land and rock strength, slope steepness and loads (natural and artificial).

The shape of a landslide body, its volume, displacement rate and landslide mechanism are diverse and depend on the combinations of conditions that determine the preparation and convergence of the landslide [15].

Landslide process - goes through the following stages:

- Pre-slide - accumulation of stresses sufficient to trigger landslide movement of rocks that shear the slope;
- landslide - displacement of rocks and gradual attenuation of movement;
- temporary stabilisation - newly acquired in the process of displacement of a stable landslide slope.

The pre-slide stage can be short-term or long-term, when for some time there is an imperceptible destructive work of atmospheric agents, groundwater and surface water, eventually leading to a landslide. The prolonged absence of obvious signs of movement on old landslide slopes cannot be an indication of their stability if the causes that triggered the landslide are still active.

Stability of a landslide slope can only be achieved if the causes of landslides are completely eliminated.

Anti-slide structures and works should be designed and carried out, as a rule, at the pre-slide stage for preventive purposes, in the most threatening parts of the slope and be part of the technical and economic

feasibility study or scheme of engineering preparation of the landslide area, which are developed for prospective solution of issues of district and urban planning, use of urban and agricultural land, for the justification of projects of industrial enterprises or linear structures, projects of general plans of cities and towns. [10].

Landslide control measures include:

- closed and open drains, overland flumes, channels and berms, drainage channels with soil and reinforced slopes, runoff interceptor flumes in thalves and on roads, flumes on landslide slopes and gully sides [9];
- horizontal, vertical and combined drains with deep and shallow embedding of drainage elements, formation drains, cut-through drains, capstans of springs and frontal outcrops and groundwater;
- ground counter-bankets (buttresses) at the foot and on stable terraces of landslide slopes with free and reinforced slope;
- retaining structures: pile reinforcements with springs and anchoring devices, bored piles, streamlined foundations, landslide retaining walls;
- slope, vertical and shaped elements coastal reinforcements (of rigid and flexible construction), artificial beaches with beach retaining structures, wave break walls and retaining walls of embankments.

- retaining walls of embankments, coastal shorelines;
 - channel-regulating structures: river buoys, spurs and flow-directing dams, barrages (overflow and overflow devices), mitigating longitudinal drains.
- Landslide control works include [8]:
- formation of artificial relief with slope stabilisation and terracing;
 - planning of slopes and terraces;
 - removal of landslides, replacement (removal) of landslide or poor quality soils with sandy-gravel soil or stone materials;
 - arrangement of filtering and waterproof coverings on slopes and terraces;
 - forest amelioration with special selection of vegetation complexes that meet the requirements for increasing the stability of landslide slopes.

Each landslide control structure or work included in the complex is intended to eliminate one of the causes or a group of causes of landslide formation.

Cost-effectiveness of landslide control structures and works is determined by the economic importance of protected objects, the safety of which in a landslide area is impossible without landslide protection. Allocation and fixing of sites in the landslide area for all types of new construction of residential buildings, industrial buildings and structures, projects of general landscaping, planting, as well as construction organisation projects and projects of works should be mandatorily coordinated with the engineering protection service of the region.

Proper installation of protective engineering structures helps to protect the area from landslides for a long time. Experience shows that the most effective way is a complex of measures and the use of different protective materials against landslides. Thus, the effectiveness of gabions and geogrids is significantly increased

with the use of geotextile sheets, which acts as an excellent reinforcing material and prevents mutual penetration of technological layers.

There are other methods of landslide protection:

- Soil consolidation. The technology consists in the use of meshes or geosynthetic grids. If you choose the former, it is enough to roll them over the site and fix them with anchors. If you choose the latter, you will first have to fold them into modules and only then connect them to the surface.

Artificial lowering of the water table is an active method of landslide protection. By reducing the groundwater level, it also reduces its damaging effect on the soil. As a result, the risk of landslide formation is reduced.

Changing the relief of the slope helps to prevent the movement of the soil base. Measures are taken to terracing the territory, to form slopes of the required steepness, to replace weak soils.

Before implementing any of the methods, it is important to carry out geological surveys, collect all information about the site and analyse how a particular landslide protection method will affect the environment.

The main task of landslide protection is to contain the landslide mass. Various methods are used for this purpose, including retaining walls. When the landslide body volume is small, retaining walls made of gabions are effective. Such constructions are especially favourable when stone is delivered from nearby quarries. The main advantage of gabion structures is their ability to retain their properties until the mesh breaks.

- Stone catching nets and barriers against landslides.

Rock trap nets are successful in preventing landslides. These protective systems are a simple but effective way of preventing landslides. It has the advantage of maintaining its performance throughout its lifetime.

The main element of this protection is galvanised mesh, which is securely fixed to the problem area by specialists.

- Another effective method of landslide protection is the reinforcement of slopes with geogrids. Being a polymer material, geogrid not only perfectly resists the movement of weak soil, but is also safe for the environment. If the rolled geogrid is rolled directly on the slope, the geogrid is used to build a retaining wall. The main advantage of geosynthetic materials is the absence of corrosion, plasticity and endurance, which together increase the long service life [10].

It is recommended to entrust the choice of protective system to specialists in the field of landslide control. This guarantees the longevity and efficiency of the structures.

References

1. Popov I.V. Engineering Geology. Moscow: Moscow State University 1959. 512 c.
2. Bondarik G.K., Penden V.V., Yarg L.A. Engineering Geodynamics. Moscow: KDU, 2007. 327 c.
3. Petrov N.F. Landslide Systems. Simple and complex landslides (classification aspects). Kishinev: Shtiyntsa, 1988. 226 c.

4. Emelyanova E. P. Basic regularities of landslide processes. Moscow: Nedra, 1972. 308 c.
5. Maslov N.N. Fundamentals of Engineering Geology and Mechanics of Soils. Moscow: Higher School, 1982. 511 c.
6. Solonenko V.P. Seismogeology and seismic zoning of the BAM route and the zone of its economic influence. - Novosibirsk, ed. "Nauka", 1979. 70 c.
7. Zolotarev G.S. Engineering Geodynamics. Moscow: Moscow State University, 1983. 378 c.
8. Slavyanov V.N. Engineering-geological forecasts of slope stability. Moscow: Stroyizdat, 1964. 153c.
9. Lomtadze V.D. Engineering Geology. Engineering geodynamics. L; Nedr, 1977. 480 c.
10. Engineering protection of territories, buildings and structures from landslides. Basic provisions, norms and rules: textbook / B. R. Aidaraliev., B. S. Ordobaev., R. S. Supanaliev., N. J. Sadabaeva., Atambek uulu M. - Bishkek: KRSU 2014. - 199 c.
11. Malamud B.D., Turcotte D.L., Guzzetti F., Reichenbach. P., «Landslide, earthquakes and erosion» Earth planet. Sci. Letters, Vol. 229, 2004. pp. 45-59.